

ATRA: A POWERFUL, LIGHTWEIGHT APPROACH TO CRAWLING

Felix Engl*, University of Bamberg, Bamberg, Germany

Abstract

In the digital age, the complexity of traditional web crawlers limits their accessibility to experts and large organizations, leaving a gap in the democratization of web data extraction. In this paper, we present Atra, an innovative solution to this challenge, designed to simplify the web crawling process while maintaining comprehensive scraping capabilities. By enabling comprehensive link extraction from a variety of document formats and archives, Atra facilitates deeper web exploration. It is also easy-to-use, making web crawling accessible to a wider audience without the need of a high investment in programming, including individuals with minimal technical skills, small organizations, and independent researchers.

MOTIVATION

Web crawlers play a critical role in navigating, indexing, and analyzing web content. Existing web crawlers, such as StormCrawler, Apache Nutch, Heritrix, and Scrapy, provide robust web crawling and data extraction solutions, but often come with a steep learning curve and require significant setup or programming skills. This complexity limits the accessibility of web crawling technologies for a wide range of users, particularly those with non-technical backgrounds or limited programming expertise. This means that not only is the research field of web search and web crawling very difficult to access, but in addition, scientific research is driven only by a small group of independent scientists and large organisations such as Microsoft or Google.

In response to these challenges, we present Atra¹, a novel web crawling solution, implemented in Rust, designed with the primary goal of scraping websites as comprehensively as possible, while ensuring ease of use and accessibility to a wide range of users. The name Atra comes from the Erigone atra, a dwarf spider with a body length of 1.8mm to 2.8mm. Not only do they play a central role in natural pest control in agriculture (aphids), but they are also aerial spiders that can travel long distances by ballooning, also known as kiting.

Atra distinguishes itself from existing web crawlers by its ability to perform link extraction from a wide variety of document formats and archives, coupled with a user-friendly interface, without the need for complex configuration or specialized knowledge. This is crucial for democratizing web crawling, by enabling small organizations, independent researchers, and hobbyists who may lack the resources to engage with more complex web crawling frameworks.

In the next chapter, we will discuss various related crawler frameworks and briefly discuss their usability in smaller projects. After a description of the currently existing Atra

features we compare Atra with the two, currently, most prominent crawlers frameworks StormCrawler and Apache Nutch. In the last chapter we describe the roadmap of Atra for reaching maturity.

RELATED SOFTWARE

In the field of web crawling, several frameworks have been developed to meet the diverse needs of researchers and practitioners. Among them, StormCrawler², Apache Nutch³, Heritrix⁴, and Scrapy⁵ have emerged as prominent tools, each with different features, tailored to specific use cases. This section provides a comparative analysis at a superficial level based on personal experience with the frameworks while working on a small crawl for a vertical search project over German schools. The following analysis will focus on describing the scalability, ease of use, flexibility, performance, and usability in smaller projects, followed by a short conclusion.

StormCrawler is designed for scalability and real-time processing, leveraging Apache Storm's [1] fault tolerance and stream processing capabilities [2]. Its modularity allows for extensive customization, making it suitable for large-scale, real-time web crawling projects. During a small project to crawl 700 websites for a vertical search system, we learned that the complexity of Apache Storm can present a steep learning curve, and the crawler requires significant setup and configuration efforts. StormCrawler also requires elaborate extensions for use case specific features like budgeting based on the crawler depth on specific domains, and extracting links and harvesting content that is not supported by default (e.g. plain text, XML, Word, PDF, JAR-Files, executable).

Apache Nutch, another scalable solution, excels at handling large data sets. It integrates seamlessly with Apache Hadoop [3] for processing and distributed storage, and benefits from a robust community and extensive support due to its long-standing presence in the field [4]. Despite its scalability and strong integration capabilities, the complexity of Apache Nutch, in combination with Hadoop, in configuration and customization may deter novices, and its extensive features may be excessive for small to medium crawling requirements. Another problem is that Apache Nutch is optimized for common crawling scenarios, meaning that specialized crawling scenarios either require a lot of configuration effort or the development of custom modules. This becomes particularly clear when facing domain specific bud-

² <https://stormcrawler.net/> (last visited 28.02.2024)

³ <https://nutch.apache.org/> (last visited 28.02.2024)

⁴ <https://github.com/internetarchive/heritrix3> (last visited 28.02.2024)

⁵ <https://scrapy.org/> (last visited 28.02.2024)

* felix.engl@uni-bamberg.de

¹ <https://github.com/FelixEngl/atra> (last visited: 21.03.2024)

getting or very strict requirements on crawling politeness⁶ like crawling with *.onion*-addresses⁷.

Heritrix is known for its specialization in web archiving [5]. Developed by the Internet Archive, it focuses on capturing a broad array of web resources for preservation purposes. While Heritrix’s emphasis on archiving makes it unparalleled for such tasks, its user interface and flexibility may not meet the needs of projects beyond web archiving. While evaluating it for our small project, we noted that Heritrix supports a wide array of link extraction methods for various common web-file formats as well as excellent budgeting for single websites. Similar to Apache Nutch, adding features for depth recording and link graphs, requires either configuration effort⁸ or custom modules. Another problem that we encountered while experimenting with Heritrix is, that some of the extraction methods are not up to date, mostly focusing on old formats or brute forcing it by matching needles with haystacks⁹.

Scrapy offers a balance between usability and functionality, characterized by its straightforward setup and high degree of flexibility for various web scraping and crawling operations [6]. Its efficient resource management and performance make it even suitable for larger crawls, although achieving distributed crawling may require additional tools or cloud-based deployments, potentially limiting its scalability and ease of use compared to frameworks explicitly designed for distributed environments. Compared to the other tools mentioned above we made the experience, that Scrapy requires less configuration and programming effort than the other frameworks. But the effort required when working with non-html-files and custom budgeting is similar.

In conclusion, all tools mentioned above are excellent tools for casual crawling tasks, and depending on the requirements of the project it is necessary to use one of them. But with regards to ease of use in smaller projects, all crawler either require a complex setup or programming for basic functions like export and extraction. For this reasons, we have developed *Atra* a minimalist, self-contained crawler for crawl tasks, without relying on external services or complex configuration and module systems, in favor of a minimalistic simplicity and robustness.

FEATURES

In this chapter we will describe the current features of *Atra*, regarding its focus on comprehensive data harvesting and link extraction, handling legacy web content, and efficient handling of crawled data. Some of the features

⁶ <https://cwiki.apache.org/confluence/display/nutch/OptimizingCrawls> (last visited 28.02.2024)

⁷ <https://cwiki.apache.org/confluence/display/NUTCH/SetupNutchAndTor> (last visited 28.02.2024)

⁸ see <https://github.com/internetarchive/heritrix3/wiki/Common-Heritrix-Use-Cases> (last visited 29.02.2024)

⁹ see <https://github.com/internetarchive/heritrix3/tree/master/modules/src/main/java/org/archive/modules/extractor> (last visited 29.02.2024)

mentioned below are tailored to meet the needs of specific user groups, ranging from research and academic communities to industry practitioners who require deep, precise web scraping capabilities.

Legacy Encoding Support

Atra incorporates advanced encoding recognition capabilities for websites, when the content-encoding header is missing, leveraging an encoding detection with *chardetng* [7] and efficient decoding based on the encoding standards [8] of the WHATWG Steering Group to support 35 different encodings. Such comprehensive encoding support—ensuring the correct interpretation and processing over a diverse range of languages and character sets—is especially crucial for web scraping in a vertical search context, where it is in some cases necessary to handle legacy and non-english content with high accuracy.

Crawling Strategy and Link Extraction

To crawl websites as efficiently as possible and reduce the number of accidental revisits, *Atra* uses a depth-first crawling strategy (see fig. 1).

Figure 1: The crawler loop of *Atra* with the link extraction and GDPR recognition feature.

The link extraction of *Atra* consists of several steps, starting with a simple content type recognition to distinguish between plain text files and archives/other resources (see fig. 1). If a plain text file is detected, *Atra* tries to derive its encoding from the response header, possible meta tags (for XML and HTML only), and encoding detection heuristics, and applies the necessary decoding to convert the content to UTF-8 for link extraction. If the plain text file is HTML, *Atra* also identifies and excludes the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹⁰ in an additional step, if configured by the

¹⁰Currently only for German websites.

user (see section GDPR-Ident). The links in a text file type are then extracted either by a specialized extractor or by a plain text heuristic. Atra’s specialized HTML extractor can also resolve links and extract data from elements, such as `<area>`, `<base>`, ``, `<iframe>`, and `<script>` tags. Furthermore it can process data URLs and uses heuristics to identify dynamic links triggered by “onclick”-events.

File Type Detection

When Atra detects non-text files, it tries to determine the file type from the content information provided, or infer the file type from the magic number or meta information. The package used to identify the magic numbers supports 437 file types¹¹.

GDPR-Ident

Atra’s *GDPR-Ident* feature represents a significant advancement in vertical/focused web crawling, addressing the critical need to identify and, if necessary, remove GDPR consent banners while crawling a website by leveraging machine learning techniques. Specifically, it uses Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) vectors derived from HTML subtrees as inputs to a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier. The SVM is trained on a curated dataset of 250 annotated documents containing a variety of GDPR consent banner implementations. This approach allows for nuanced detection of GDPR-relevant content across different web pages. In empirical evaluations of the prototype implementation [9], we observed a remarkable accuracy rate of 96% in identifying GDPR banners, see table 1. This high level of accuracy also underscores the effectiveness of combining TF-IDF vectorization with SVM classification in addressing the complexities of regulatory compliance in web crawling.¹²

		True Label		
		Positive	Negative	Total
Predicted Label	Positive	27	0	27
	Negative	2	21	23
	Total	29	21	50

Table 1: The confusion matrix obtained by testing the prototype of the GDPR-identification system. [9]

Data Handling

Atra is also designed to archive websites as completely as possible. Hence, Atra does not only collect all header information of a response, but also collects and analyzes all files encountered on a website. For storing the crawled data Atra uses a combination of Notation3 (n3), WARC/1.1 and binary files (for data exceeding 100 Megabyte¹³). Internal

¹¹https://docs.rs/file-format/0.24.0/file_format/ (last visited 28.02.2024)

¹²Prototype code and research will be published alongside Atra.

¹³Otherwise, the binary files are stored with BASE64 encoding in the WARC-file

data, such as skip-pointers, metadata and the overall crawl state for every URL are stored with RocksDB¹⁴.

Modes and Clustering

Due to the fact, that Atra follows a philosophy of simplicity and self-containment it only supports three different modes: *single*, *multi*, and *cluster*. The following paragraph will explain the different modes and describe how they can be used in research and practice in general.

Single-Mode *Single-mode* allows to crawl a single website with Atra using a Command Line Interface (CLI). When starting Atra in *single-mode*, the only information required is the agent name, seed URL, and target crawl depth. The seed is then scraped as completely as possible.

Multi-Mode *Multi-mode* runs in multiple threads on a single machine to crawl multiple seeds at once. Basically, Atra behaves in this mode like in *cluster-mode*, but it omits the boilerplate for controlling crawl politeness between multiple machines as well as fail-safe mechanisms required in a network. *Multi-mode* is started via CLI, but instead of simple commands, Atra now requires two configuration files (`atra.ini` and `crawl.yaml`). `atra.ini` contains general application settings like cache sizes, while `crawl.yaml` configures the crawl behavior in a more sophisticated way (e.g. user agent, politeness and domain specific crawl budgets).

Cluster-Mode The *cluster-mode* is similar to *multi-mode*, but instead of a single instance on a single machine, there are multiple instances on multiple machines working in a computing cluster as depicted in fig. 2. In *cluster-mode*, Atra needs at least two instances per machine. One of these instances, from here on referred to as “orchestrator”, is handling the work balance, connection to the cluster, crawler politeness, and handling subordinates. The other instances on the machine (called “subordinates”), are used for crawling and data collection.

In a cluster each orchestrator is assigned a specific range of domains and other orchestrators in the cluster send URLs, matching this specific domain-range, to the assignee. When the cluster is running, all orchestrators periodically renegotiate their domain assignments to accommodate uneven workloads. Additionally, as a fail-safe mechanism, the orchestrators periodically synchronize the information about the workload and URL of the orchestrator via the Paxos protocol [10] (see fig. 3). If a participant drops out, and is therefore missing during the regular negotiations, the last known state of the dropout is used to crawl the probably missing websites with an other participant.

COMPARISON

To highlight the differences between Atra and other crawlers, we compare the performance of Atra with Storm-

¹⁴<https://rocksdb.org/> (last visited 21.03.2024)

Figure 2: An exemplary view of a machine running an orchestrator with subordinates. Additionally the example depicts the communication between Machine A in a cluster with two other participants.

Update Package			
Orchestrator ID: <MAC> or <IP> or <Unique Name in Cluster>			
Update ID: <Incremental ID> // All updates from are participant have to be applied in order			
Current time of Orchestrator : <UTC Timestamp> // Can be out of sync between machines			
Workload Information:			
Domain	Workload	Timestamp (UTC)	Recrawl In
opensearchfoundation.org	5min	2024-03-01 7:05:56.5768348 +00:00:00	7 Days
...	...		
URL Information:			
URL	STATE	Timestamp (UTC)	LSH
https://opensearchfoundation.org/	Stored	2024-03-01 7:00:56.5768348 +00:00:00	1536:J2ap3J7EJs...FL0u
...

Figure 3: A schematic of an update package. The workload information consists of the domains crawled by the orchestrator and information when the crawl is finished and when a recrawl is necessary. The URL information consists of the URL-state (e.g. "Discovered", "Stored") and a locality sensitive hash (abbreviated with LSH).

Crawler, as well as Apache Nutch, under uniform test conditions in table 2. Then we use a comparison table of the most common requirements for vertical crawls to compare the three contestants (see table 3).

Performance

Since StormCrawler and Apache Nutch are designed to crawl in a cluster, this paper does not analyse crawl speed, but single machine efficiency. This is because the pages/sec metric in a cluster does not depend on the efficiency of a program, but on scaling. Furthermore, Atra is intended to be used in smaller companies or by individuals who may not have access to large cluster configurations. Therefore, we decided to compare all three contestants based on their memory footprint during the operation of each crawler in a minimalistic setup.

In order to keep the comparison between the crawlers unbiased with respect to a particular operating system or special configurations, we used the Docker container configurations for each crawler as suggested in the respective crawler manuals^{15,16} (see table 2). Assuming that the Docker containers are using the bare minimum required to run the crawlers, we have adopted the Docker container memory metrics for our comparison. This also has the advantage that we can ensure that we are measuring not only the memory usage of the crawler tasks themselves, but also any in-memory buffers used by the OS when writing to a disk.

To mitigate the influence of the caches, we recorded the memory footprint of the cold systems and the warmed up

¹⁵<https://github.com/apache/nutch/> (last visited: 20.03.2024)

¹⁶<https://github.com/DigitalPebble/stormcrawler-docker> (last visited: 20.03.2024)

system after crawling five seeds to an absolute depth of three (resulting in roughly 5000 crawled web-pages). To account for variability and to avoid misrepresentation, especially for Java-based programs where garbage collection can skew the results, we computed the total memory usage by rounding the minima down and the maxima up to the nearest hundred.

The results of our measurements show a stark disparity in resource utilization (see table 2): Atra’s memory efficiency is underscored by a footprint of 15 to 60 megabytes. Conversely, Apache Nutch requires 300 to 500 megabytes in its local operation mode within the provided Docker container. StormCrawler’s requirements dwarf its counterparts, requiring between 1,500 and 2,000 megabytes due to its multi-service architecture.

	Apache StormCrawler	Apache Nutch	Atra
MIN (MB)	1,500	300	15
MAX (MB)	2,000	500	60
Docker Service Count	5	1	1

Table 2: Comparison of the memory consumption of StormCrawler, Apache Nutch, and Atra during operation, according to the Docker container memory metrics. Measurements were taken five times, from the cold and warmed up system, after crawling five seeds to an absolute depth of three. The lowest (MIN) and highest (MAX) values were then rounded to the nearest hundred. The last row shows the number of Docker containers required to use the crawler on a system.

Feature-Comparison

This section is a comparison of the basic features (see table 3) available in StormCrawler, Apache Nutch and Atra.

Environment Regarding the environment, it is noteworthy that Atra has the least environmental requirements, while the other crawlers require some kind of framework or runtime (see table 3).

Indexing Looking at the available indexing methods of the three crawlers, only Atra currently supports WARC/1.1 + Community Annotations¹⁷ and Notation3. Due to the fact that Atra does not perform any filtering or other pre-processing steps (except GDPR), it is sufficient for Atra to combine these standards with skip-pointers and RocksDB to provide an efficient method for managing the crawled data, without relying on external services. Atra’s roadmap includes expanding its indexing capabilities to encompass Solr and Elasticsearch, aligning with industry standards provided by StormCrawler and Apache Nutch, as well as improving the user-comfort.

¹⁷see <https://iipc.github.io/warc-specifications/specifications/warc-format/warc-1.1-annotated/> (last visited: 20.04.2024)

Link Extraction As mentioned in the previous text, one of Atra’s goals is to be a minimalist and self-sufficient crawler with a high link discovery rate. Therefore, Atra supports the most common online formats natively (see table 3). In addition, Atra uses heuristics to extract links from unknown file types as well as raw text (see "Binary" table 3). In future releases of Atra, we will also provide an optional REST API for Tika servers to comply with industry standards. For JavaScript link extraction, Atra currently parallels the capabilities of Apache Nutch.

Further Features Unique to Atra is its GDPR recognition/filtering and live web graph building by streaming Notation3 tuples to a file. Similar to StormCrawler and Apache Nutch, Atra supports Single Page Application (SPA) handling. But instead of using the Chrome DevTools protocol, Atra will use "Servo", an embedded browser. However, to comply with industry standards, Atra will also support the Chrome DevTools protocol as an alternative.

FUTURE WORK

Looking at the road map of Atra, our vision encompasses a comprehensive suite of enhancements aimed at reaching a position as minimalistic, robust and user friendly crawler on par with other state of the art crawlers.

Firstly, we intend to significantly expand the range of file formats that Atra can process for link extraction. Specifically for JavaScript, we plan to improve JavaScript link extraction by enhancing the existing extraction method, as well as executing and analysing JavaScripts (JSs) variables and communication in an embedded, sandboxed environment powered by V8 [11]. These enhancements will allow Atra to dig deeper into web resources, uncovering connections and data across an even wider range of document and media types, making the crawler more useful for research and analysis. We also plan to add support for various protocols, such as FTP, to broaden the available sources for data collection.

A key goal of Atra is to use Servo, an embeddable web browser engine written in Rust, to handle SPAs. Servo has recently seen a resurgence in activity and development, supported by external funding¹⁸, which is expected to lead to a stable embedding API. This upcoming integration aims to enhance Atra’s SPA handling capabilities while maintaining its design principles of autonomy, security and efficiency.

In response to the specific needs of law enforcement and cybersecurity professionals, we also plan to integrate support for navigating the dark web through TOR, with a particular focus on onion address crawling. This capability will provide essential tools for secure and anonymous investigations within the confines of the Dark Web.

These envisioned enhancements to Atra are designed to reinforce its core principles while addressing the dynamic challenges of web crawling. Through these strategic developments, we aim to deliver a tool that is not only more powerful

¹⁸"Servo to Advance in 2023" - <https://servo.org/blog/2023/01/16/servo-2023/> (last visited 29.02.2024)

	Apache StormCrawler	Apache Nutch	Atra
Environment			
OS	Cross-Platform	Cross-Platform	Windows, Linux
Written in	Java	Java	Rust
Dependencies	Apache Storm	Apache Hadoop	-
Docker	+	+	+
Scalable	+	+	o
Indexers			
WARC	1.0	1.0	1.1 + Annotations
Solr	+	+	o
Elasticsearch	+	+	o
SQL	+	-	-
AWS CloudSearch	+	+	-
OpenSearch	+	-	-
Rabbit	-	+	-
CSV	-	+	-
N3	-	-	+
Link Extractors			
HTML	Native	Native	Native
JS	-	Native	Native
CSS	-	-	o (Native)
PDF	Tika	Tika	o (Native)
DOCX/XLSX/PPTX	Tika	Tika	o (Native)
TXT	Tika	Tika	Native
ZIP	-	Native	o (Native)
BIN (Binary)	-	-	Native
TIKA-REST	-	-	o (Native)
Further Features			
GDPR-Recognition	-	-	+
Single Page Applications	Selenium	Selenium	o (Native/Selenium)
Dedublication	-	+	o

Table 3: A feature comparison between Apache StormCrawler, Apache Nutch and Atra. An “o” denotes planned features in future releases of Atra, that are deemed necessary to reach full maturity or to comply with industry standards.

and versatile but also remains user-friendly and accessible to a wide array of users, from researchers to cybersecurity professionals and law enforcement agencies worldwide.

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